

ELECTRO/ACOUSTIC SOUNDPAINTING RECOGNITION: COORDINATION AND COMMUNICATION BETWEEN HUMAN AND MACHINE PERFORMERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an approach to Soundpainting-based gesture recognition, using a machine learning framework developed in Python. This project builds upon our previous work, which focused on incorporating computational musical agents into an electroacoustic performance ensemble. In so doing, the system enables direct control of machine agents via gesture recognition. While specifically designed for *thee Doug Van Nort Electro-Acoustic Orchestra (EAO)*, our approach offers flexible training and model generation for other composers and Soundpainting environments. At the time of writing the system is capable of detecting 41 Soundpainting gestures, and is modular and extensible to allow for expansion of the gesture dictionary.

Gesture recognition is completed using four separate models, each targeting a separate vertical slice of the Soundpainter. Additionally, each gesture is broken down into “gesture components” (one or two combined individual hand gestures), which taken together make up a full combination gesture. Technical details and system design justifications are presented for model training, gesture recognition, and accompanying Max-based control patches. Initial testing results are presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper builds upon and is inspired by our previously published system for co-creative musical play with autonomous computational agents [1] [2]. The system we present is capable of gesture recognition for “Soundpainting” conducting, allowing machine agents to participate as active members of an electro-acoustic performance ensemble. Soundpainting is a gestural language described by its creator, Walter Thompson, as a practice where a composer “communicates a series of signs using hand and body gestures indicating specific and/or aleatoric material to be performed by the group. The Soundpainter develops the responses of the performers, molding and shaping them into the composition then signs another series of gestures, a phrase, and continues in this process of composing the piece.” [3].

In our previous work, the machine agents were designed to take part in a mixed human/machine electroacoustic en-

semble performance, with *thee Doug Van Nort Electro-Acoustic Orchestra* (henceforth referred to as EAO). The ensemble is led by the second author via both pre-composed musical structures, and real-time composition based on what they refer to as *Electro/Acoustic Soundpainting (ESP)* – an extended form of Soundpainting that introduces new gesture and concepts that are specific to electroacoustic music. Human members of the ensemble performed alongside computational agents which are trained on recordings of previous EAO sessions. This results in agents which behave as musical “doppelgangers” of the participating human players. The logic for agents is built upon IRCAM’s Dicy2 [4] [5], a Max-based system which can be fed live and recorded audio to learn temporal and timbral relations of musical content. It was found that a shortcoming with this setup was that all control messages to the computational agents needed to be relayed by a human performer using a software interface, interpreting the ESP gestures of the conductor.

Here, we outline our system design and approach for automatic gesture recognition for Soundpainting conducting, which alleviates the need for human control of conducting to machine agents. Given our focus on ESP, the system is designed to accommodate extensions to the Soundpainting vocabulary, and allows for idiosyncratic gesture content for different composers by utilizing a streamlined model training process. While the system has been designed for the second author, the flexibility of training and model generation makes the gesture recognition composer-agnostic, and able to be adapted to the styles of other Soundpainting practitioners.

The gesture recognition logic is built upon skeletal/hand landmark tracking via MediaPipe [6]. Gestures are separated into “gesture components” which target individual hand gestures, rather than recognition using compound multi-hand formations. Justifications and approaches of the system design are presented in section 3. Accuracy results from initial testing are reported in section 4.

2. RELATED WORKS

2.1 Soundpainting

Soundpainting is a gesture-based composition/conducting language created by Walter Thompson in 1974 to communicate non-verbally with players during performance. The lexicon has since grown to include more gestures, and can be further expanded or modified to meet the needs of a given composer or ensemble. The practice includes a substantial gestural vocabulary, cited at 1500 gestures as of

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2024 [3]. Each gesture consists of hand and finger positions relative to the body. Gestures may convey instructions on *Who*, *What*, *How*, and *When* for musical content. *Who* gestures relate to groups, sub-groups, or individuals that are the target for the upcoming gestures. *What* refers to the type of material to perform (eg. pointillism, long tone). *How* gestures provide instruction on the character of the material (eg. volume, pitch, roughness), and may be intentionally left out of a gestural statement to allow the performer to choose their own approach to the conducted *What* content. *When* provides a timing instruction for the gestural statement. These timing commands may include gestures like fading in/out, or instantaneous enter/exits.

Marc Duby discusses Soundpainting in the context of improvisatory music, highlighting its role within the communal act of performing [7]. Duby places the musical action resulting from Soundpainting on a “continuum between organization and total freedom”, noting the range of potential play modalities for both composers and players. Soundpainting composition performed without *how* gestures moves closer to Duby’s conception of “total freedom” which comes via improvisation, while still being able to be shaped by organizing *who*, *what*, and *when* instructions. The resulting interpretation by players defines a unique performance paradigm where strict instruction vs open expression is continually in flux. Navigating this relationship is key for composers to understand the tendencies of the ensemble, and inversely this is necessary for performers who must be able to match the intention of the given instructions. In the words of Thompson:

“At what point does the Soundpainter’s creative direction lapse to be overtaken by the creative impetus of the ensemble or the individual? Never. Each Soundpainter chooses how active, how simple and/or how complicated the phrasing will be according to what is taking place in the moment. If the Soundpainter decides to sign less, for a few minutes or so, they are doing so because they would like that point in the composition to be more open to the players. The Soundpainter would be signing less for a couple of key reasons. 1 – they desire the performers to develop a certain section of the piece at their own rate. 2 – they are leaving the section open to chance where the Soundpainter will search for material to further the composition... The Soundpainter is the composer at all times. They decide and govern every aspect of the piece just as the traditional composer does.” [8] [9]

As noted previously, The ESP language used by within the EAO context utilizes the syntax and many gestures from the Soundpainting language, while introducing new “gesture-concepts” that are tailored to electroacoustic music creation, drawing on languages and frameworks including deep listening, spectromorphology and aural sonology [10].

2.2 Gesture Recognition for Soundpainting

Pellegrini et al. present the first prototype for Soundpainting gesture tracking. Using both captured image and depth data from a Microsoft Kinect, the system performs skeletal tracking of the composer for gesture recognition [11]. A corpus of 20 gestures performed 5 times each by a Soundpainting conductor was used to generate the recognition model’s training data. Their paper presents a series of speculative outcomes of Soundpainting recognition systems, discussing the performance potential of computer agents as musicians in an ensemble, the utility of learning Soundpainting through live feedback from a system, and the development of new sound design interfaces using embodied control.

Jáuregui et al. present their system designed for Soundpainting recognition, which also used depth and skeletal data from the Kinect [12]. The system is trained to track six gestures: whole group, rest of group, wait, scanning, silence, and off. Additionally, the system is trained to recognize a neutral gesture, and two intermediate gestures which are used to avoid misreads when in-between other gestures. These gestures were then mapped to electronic sound generation with Pure Data. The paper reports on a study of the system done in two environments - one with a live performance setting, and the other in a learning environment. Their reported results show that the system was able to recognize gestures, but with a lower accuracy than two human participants. In the learning environment, high user engagement was reported from the sound feedback. Visual feedback was highlighted as important for Soundpainters to understand the system’s perception of their action, and allowed them to adjust gestures accordingly.

Parmentier et al. developed an open-source system for Soundpainting recognition in Max [13]. The system allows users to use a variety of input hardware (webcams, Kinect, motion tracking gloves, etc.) to track their gestures. Hand landmark tracking is done via MediaPipe, running in Max using Node.js. A key feature of their approach is the ability of users to add gestures by defining new examples the system. Gestures are recognized using dynamic time warping via the external software solution Wekinator. Output of the recognition is sent to another Max external package, *bach*, for sonification.

Van Nort developed a Soundpainting recognition system using a combination of dynamic time warping and neural net methods from the Wekinator system, for use specifically in the EAO context [2]. This system was used in a number of public performances for the *Intersubjective Soundings* [14] and *Quarantine: A Telematic nO(t)pera* projects [15]. Our new system is inspired by this past work both in terms of the ways it demonstrated the creative richness and potential for machine-mediated expansion of electroacoustic ensembles (on the one hand), and room for improving upon the challenges of accurate recognition (on the other). This is particularly true in a dynamic context where the ESP language is often used with substantial variations in timing, spatial location and orientation, merging co-present performers and screen-based telematic ones.

3. SYSTEM

With the range of available Soundpainting recognition systems, why might a user favour our approach over another? Our solution is currently equipped to recognize 41 unique combination gestures used within Soundpainting, making it the largest set of gestures in a published system. The system is developed using Python, leveraging widely used packages for machine learning [16] and data handling [17]. While node-based coding and multimedia development environments like Max have a large user base, text-based programming has a significantly higher user base - with Python having the highest popularity of all programming languages (as of March 2025) [18] [19]. Creating our approach for a well-known language like Python allows more programmers who are familiar with the language to extend and tweak the gesture recognition script as they see fit. Development in Python also allows for greater distribution to machines which may not have access to environments like Max, and avoids the requirement of paid licenses for users in order to edit and save personal changes to the code. Each of the scripts involved the data gathering, training, and gesture recognition are created in Python, streamlining the use of the system and avoiding the use of many disparate software environments.

MediaPipe [6] [20] is used for skeletal and hand landmark tracking for both model training, and live gesture recognition. MediaPipe was chosen as the basis for data collection in our system because of its fast real-time performance and flexible architecture using lightweight pre-trained models. MediaPipe is not used directly for the classification of the performed gestures, only landmark data of the performer's hands is captured before further processing and gesture classification. After installation, our system is designed to run with minimal technical setup. All tracking is done using a consumer grade webcam to remain accessible and portable. The system generates a set of four models trained on individual hand gestures, each targeting a different height in relation to the users body, which will be discussed further in the following section. While our setup is configured for output to a Max patch controlling the ensemble's computational agents, output from the Python script is formatted as OSC messages and thus can easily be routed to a user's choice of software.

3.1 Training

Training data is fully composed of hand landmark coordinates from MediaPipe. Hand positions are calculated relative to the body of the user, rather than global screen space location. The midpoint between both shoulder landmarks is used as a central reference point on the body for position calculations. Using relative coordinates of hand landmarks avoids the need for precise positioning of the composer in the video frame for gesture performance, and allows them to move naturally around the space (other than the necessity of orientation towards the camera). This relative positioning also aligns well with Soundpainting conducting practice, as most gestures have varied syntactic meaning based on vertical and horizontal offsets from the body.

Four height ranges are established for the player during training, each resulting in an individual gesture model. These are used to train only the relevant gesture data at each vertical slice of the body. This separation of models helps filter out misreads on gestures which are not performed at certain heights. The ranges are:

- Legs (below waist)
- Torso (above waist, below neck)
- Head (above neck, below top of head)
- Above head

These can be seen listed in Fig.3 for both left and right hands.

Our approach allows for training to be completed in a guided environment which lets composers perform gestures as they see fit. The system prompts users to perform "gesture components", individual hand gestures which are used in combination to arrive at a final output gesture (what would then be interpreted as a full Soundpainting gesture). A total of 46 gesture components (one-handed gestures) are currently implemented as these are required in order to recognize the set of commonly used EAO combination gestures which we have focused on (listed in the following subsection). Users are prompted on the current gesture component to perform, and are given an example of what Soundpainting gesture the component may be used in for context. Landmark values resulting from the performed gesture are saved into an individual comma separate value (.csv) file. A default of 125 samples per gesture component are taken, with each sample consisting of the 21 hand landmarks captured by MediaPipe. This gives users time to settle into their ideal performance of the gesture while training, and allows for the system to track any subtle variances in performance which may occur. Training can be completed individually without the need to manually annotate recorded data, and the process is designed to transition seamlessly between each model. Once data is collected and a csv file is created for each gesture component, each height-based model can be built using the collection of resulting files. Models are built using Scikit-learn's SGDClassifier for linear classification with stochastic gradient descent, and a one-vs-rest configuration for each gesture component. For each gesture, the system performs a check against each class of potential gesture components and returns the most similar gesture from the training data. This architecture was chosen to take advantage of the typical gesture content within soundpainting. While there are many dynamic gestures which can challenge this approach, a large amount of relevant ESP gestures in the EAO context can be performed as a static position relative to the body. Some gestures like "exit" are comprised of multiple parts - a prompt with hands held above the head, and an activation by sweeping the hands down in front of the body. In these circumstances, combination gestures are checked in multiple stages and the Soundpainter needs to perform each stage of the gesture to be classified successfully. This architectural approach also allows for quick retraining of individual classifiers before building the model again, since

Figure 1. The gesture recognition script setup interface. Users may choose a target trained model, and various gesture or OSC settings.

each set of samples can be overwritten without affecting the samples of other trained gestures.

From other Soundpainting recognition approaches, users have encountered challenges with precision in performing gestures. Jáuregui et al. note, “Some gestures were not properly recognized in their first executions since the Soundpainter was accustomed to performing it in a different way from the trained posture” [12]. This phenomena can be avoided through practice or repetition to learn the trained hand shape, however, this can also be addressed at the time of model training by learning the ideal shape for each user. Conductors do not need to learn an “optimal” hand shape, but simply need to have a reproducible shape that they understand for each gesture component.

Some height models share gesture components, though these are re-trained per model in order to better capture their characteristics as there are poses which are not easy to perform the same at different angles. Separately generating a model for each height results in a strong fit towards a particular use case and environmental setting where the models are trained, though this approach is potentially less transferable to other users, necessitating the quick and seamless training process.

3.2 Gesture Recognition

Once a set of models is trained and generated, users can run the recognition script via a setup UI to pick their desired model, and have access to other configurations (Fig. 1). The system does not attempt to match both hands in one combined set of data. Rather, gesture results for each hand are parsed individually. As four models have been developed (one for each height range as outlined above), the height of the hand relative to the section of the user’s body is taken into consideration first. If the hand is below the waist for example, then the classifier will only check against the “Legs” model, which contains relevant gesture components (one handed gestures) for all “combination gestures” (multi-hand Soundpainting gestures) which may be performed there.

After gesture classification for each hand is complete, the system attempts to match a combination gesture. All Soundpainting gestures are defined in the system as a set of

Figure 2. Logical flow of gesture capture, model selection, gesture component classification, and combination gesture dictionary query.

one or two gesture components. A diagram of this process can be seen in Fig. 2. For example, a combination gesture of “Tempo” consists of a raised fist and a horizontal hand over the raised arm. In another gesture, this raised fist is also used to signify “Volume” control, when accompanied by the other hand producing an “V” shape. This segmented approach allows for clear definition of Soundpainting gestures via individual hand actions. Gestures with temporal/dynamic content do not need to consider both hands as part of training, greatly reducing misreads of quickly performed gesture components. Grace periods are implemented to avoid any sudden misreads conflicting with a currently performed gesture if the tracking becomes jittery. These grace periods are set using a number of processed frames by the system (default 3), and are established for recognizing a new gesture (gesture length), and ending the current gesture (gesture reset).

Separating the recognition of both hands allows additionally for added redundancy checks on variations, or similarly-displayed gesture components. While training allows for composers/users to perform gestures in the manner they wish, there are still cases where gestures are recognizably close or are formed with subtle differences. The Soundpainting gesture dictionary in the system can be expanded to account for these near misses.

The position and orientation of hands relative to the body is another measure used to check against the validity of a currently recognized hand gesture. There are four states which are considered, comprised of palm and arm components:

- Palm up, arm down
- Palm down, arm down
- Palm up, arm up
- Palm down, arm up

These component states are calculated by relative X position of the little finger and thumb for roll (wrist rotation), and relative Y position of the end of the middle finger and base of the wrist for pitch (wrist orientation). The calculations for palm orientation must also take into consideration

Figure 3. A user performing the “Density” gesture. The Max interface for monitoring and parsing incoming gesture messages is visible in the bottom section. Group 5 is depicted as currently selected.

which side of the body is being detected, or an unintentional mirroring of the hand state will occur. Display of this tracking to users can be seen in Fig. 3, with the “Orient” status for both right and left hands.

The system is currently configured to detect 41 ESP gestures which are very commonly used in EAO. These are: fade, scanline, pitch, volume, tempo, density, tone, noise, pointillism, silence, sustain, start (go), end (exit), groups 1-7, subgroups (6-1, 6-2, 7-1, 7-2), range, rest of group (left and right), whole group, palettes (1-5), “and”, morph, volume, with, tear up, within, without, and crossover.

Finally, when combination gestures, hand, or body landmarks are detected, Open Sound Control (OSC) formatted messages are created and sent to a target IP address via UDP. By default this output targets the user’s local computer, though messages may also be directed to remote addresses.

3.3 Controlling Musical Machine Agents

OSC messages are sent from the Python gesture recognition script to a Max patch designed to parse incoming Soundpainting statements. As outlined in section 2.1, Soundpainting may target subgroups of performers, timbral, rhythmic, temporal content, and more. A simplified presentation view is created in the patch so that the composer may monitor currently targeted groups, and to ensure their performed gestures are processed correctly (visible at the bottom of Fig. 3). This configuration is setup for the typical group structures of EAO, including subgroups for groups 6 and 7 (lower bar of groups).

Some performance gestures require continuous data or body landmarks in order to be meaningful for both players and the agents. For example in Fig. 3 “Density” refers to the duration of time between discrete events. This is a useful gesture to signal an increase or decrease in the the rate of activity of performed material. For the computational agents, receiving a message that a density gesture has been performed has no meaning without providing a value as-

Figure 4. The agent staging patch, which translates incoming gesture messages into agent musical content instructions.

sociated with the gesture. After parsing input gesture content, continuous control values are generated for these gestures from 0 to 1 in the accompanying Max patch. These values correspond with the embodied action and meaning of the gesture. Again in the case of “Density”, values approaching 0 are increasingly less dense (hands further from the users head), while values approaching 1 are increasingly more dense (hands closer to their head). This is also depicted in the Max console in Fig. 3.

To align with the typical participant count of the core EAO group and to facilitate diverse interactions, six computational agents were developed for our performance context. Each agent was designed to mirror a specific EAO musician, drawing from a personalized dataset compiled from past rehearsals and live performances. These datasets captured the stylistic tendencies and sonic characteristics of each performer, effectively creating a virtual counterpart to perform with the ensemble. The selected training material of previous EAO rehearsals and performances encompassed a broad range of timbral and dynamic variation, ensuring that the agents could engage meaningfully with both human musicians as well as other agents. For a more in-depth breakdown of the complete machine agent system logic for sound production please refer to Hoy and Van Nort (2024) [1].

Computational agents receive messages via a “staging” patch; an interface developed initially for manual control by a human intermediary. This patch has been updated to accommodate gesture recognition statements to prompt agents on what content to play (Fig. 4). Multiple modes allow messages to be prompted and then later “pushed” to agents, following a relevant *when* Soundpainting instruction from the conductor. “Live” mode allows messages from gestures to be immediately relayed to agents, which is comparable to the Soundpainting “launch mode” in which players are prompted to immediately follow continually changing content, rather than wait for a “go” gesture. The staging patch also depicts the current states of each agent, acting as visual confirmation for the conductor that gestures were received. Total latency from performed gesture, classification, and processing into agent control syntax is low (~200-300 ms depending on performed gesture), and aligns well with typical human timescales for perception and understanding of intended playing content.

4. RESULTS

Cross-performer testing of the presented gesture recognition system was conducted by both authors. A trained set of models was established by the first author and was evaluated for accuracy. Gestures were performed 10 times by each conductor in order to assess their recognition consistency and repeatability. A short time-window (~ 1 -2 seconds) was allowed for the system to recognize the gesture components while still performing the gesture naturally. This amount of time for natural performance varies for each gesture, and the latency of a human with moderate-to-advanced understanding of Soundpainting was used as a benchmark of acceptable delay. Gestures recognized after a duration which felt natural to performance were marked as incorrect. Taking this phenomenological approach, the time thresholds used for testing (and also employed in the system) align with the duration it typically takes a human performer to be able to follow and process the gesture's intent within the performed gesture syntax. Natural performance of gestures was ensured to gauge usability in real-world performance settings, rather than using deliberately slow gestures which might be beneficial for recognition. Gestures are further only counted as correct if performed on the first try with minimal repositioning and without misclassification.

4.1 Gesture Accuracy

Results show a clear set of reliable and accurate classifications which were stable between both composers (Fig. 5). Values are displayed as averages for correctly identified gestures between both authors. The resulting accuracy values depict the interoperable nature of the system, allowing generated training models to be used and accurate for other composers. The combined average of the system for all tested gestures is 78.3%. From the reported values in Fig. 5, pitch and smooth have not been accounted for in the total count of 41 reproducible gestures, as their performance was not reliable. Without the inclusion of pitch and smooth this overall average accuracy increases to 81.9%. 32 of the 41 gestures were performed with accuracies $\geq 75\%$.

Nine gestures were performed without any misreads in testing, resulting in 100% accuracy for both users. These were volume, tone, noise, group (2, 3, 5, 6), rest of group (right side), and palette 5. Nearly all of these gestures are static and are performed with clearly visible finger positions. Volume is the one exception, which has the potential to obscure the raised fist gesture component used to track the combination gesture. The success of this set of gestures points to the overall strength of the system in classification of static gestures, even with a large amount of classes available to determine from. Relatively minimal variations between gestures are also handled well. This is also the case for dynamic gestures, which maintain finger and wrist orientations while moving. Crossover, fade, scanline, and morph include moving components, but all scored accuracies $\geq 82\%$. This is likely due to their relatively static gesture components. While orientation of the arm or hand may change for these gestures, the overall form of the relative finger positions remains the same.

Figure 5. Average accuracy of performed gesture classification between both users (Accuracy sorted high to low).

4.2 Challenges

Some trained gestures which contain more dynamic content beyond wrist/arm orientation failed to be useful in testing. These include multi-stage gestures or continuous movements. For continuous movement gestures such as initiating “Shapeline” mode, a “start” and “end” gesture were established. These findings suggest the need for a mixed classification approach using temporal (Dynamic Time Warping) or sequencing classification techniques (Hidden Markov Models) for non-static gestures. Gestures which failed to be classified correctly are not reported above and are not included in the final count of recognized gestures.

Accuracy results for “rough” and “tear up” reveal one potential disadvantage with the training process, as these two gestures had the highest variance of accuracy between each conductor. For the first author who trained the model, ac-

curacies were 90% and 70% respectively, while the second author was not able to have any accurate gesture classifications. Testing footage reveals that the second author performed these gestures with a more dynamic approach, while the first author had a more static representation for both gestures. Where bespoke model creation per user is a benefit to accurate classification of gestures, using models trained by another user may result in the idiosyncrasies of a trained gesture to be incompatible with the style of another user.

5. DISCUSSION

The presented system follows in the steps of similar Soundpainting recognition systems, and achieves the goal of “computer as musician” put forth by Pellegrini et al. [11]. Their paper theorized on the potential for placing the computer itself within a Soundpainting lead ensemble, both in physical and musical space. Our system achieves this by granting each computational agent a numbered group which other human players belong to, which can be addressed automatically via Soundpainting composition. Each agent is assigned a group which consists of other human players, and the staging interface may also be used to change groups of agents, updating routing to send control messages to the appropriate target.

As discussed here and in our previous publication, Soundpainting is an interpretative interaction between composer and player (both human and machine). Where our previous approach required a mediating human in between the composer and computational agents, the logic for parsing the syntax of soundpainting material must actively take part in interpreting the goals and action of the composer. Replacing humans in this role ideally makes the process more objective, and more closely and accurately able to follow the action of the composer without the need to translate this to some input on the control interface.

Where some implementations in other systems enforce a particular order of *Who*, *What*, *How*, and *When* gestures, our system maintains a freedom of expressing soundpainting gestures in (mostly) any order. There are some circumstances where this strict ordering is necessary. For example with “shapeline”, performers immediately begin to fluidly follow conductor movements as soon as the gesture has finished – and so so a target group must first be provided. However, in most cases with the system, Soundpainting composers are able to interchangeably prepare content, targets, and other character-shaping gestures.

While the gesture recognition models are trained by the composer, there are still inaccuracies which may arise from the nature of the performance environment. The system is only able to capture what the composer allows it to see via its camera, and any obfuscating movements, poor lighting, or clothing blending with the background can interrupt that direct communication. While miscommunication is not the goal of the system, this too can lead to interesting musical directions which the composer may have not considered. Just as a human may misinterpret or miss a series of gestures, the agents might also if a gesture is misinterpreted. This echoes Duby’s characterization of Soundpainting as

being on the “continuum between organization and total freedom” [7], which moves between structured compositional intent and the fluid, emergent nature of live improvisation – in this case through the idiosyncratic interpretations of both human and machine.

6. FUTURE WORK AND CONCLUSIONS

Internal testing was done using a relatively limited performance dataset of 20 performances per gesture. Testing can be expanded to further report on recall, precision, and F score of individual gesture components. User studies should be completed in order to gauge quantitative success of the system for those outside of the DisPerSion Lab ecosystem. These studies may consider gesture recognition accuracy, composer training & ease of use, and gauge expressiveness of available gestures in performance. Responses of players with a deep familiarity with Soundpainting should also be considered to understand the effect of providing players with live transcription and a history of performed gestures.

This paper has presented a technological follow-up to our previous research on integrating computational agents into electroacoustic ensemble performance. Building upon our earlier system, which required a human intermediary to interpret Soundpainting gestures for machine agents, this work introduced an automated gesture recognition system that enables direct communication between the conductor and computational performers. The system is designed for use with *thee Doug Van Nort Electro-Acoustic Orchestra* and is configured to detect 41 separate ESP gestures, the largest set of Soundpainting-based gestures compared to other published systems.

A key advancement of this system is training and generation of four separate recognition models, each targeting a distinct vertical section of the conductor’s body. Additionally, the recognition framework decomposes Soundpainting gestures into “gesture components,” allowing for precise classification of individual hand positions and movements before assembling them into full combination gestures. This modular approach has improved recognition accuracy (a total average of 81.9% for the 41 gestures), while maintaining the ability to adapt to other composers and use cases via flexible, and guided model training.

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